

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

COVID-19 Pandemic: Macroeconomic Impacts and Understanding its Implications for Jordan

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Abstract

These editorial reviews the potential short- and long-term macroeconomic impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic according to the data announced in Jordan, Provides evidence of certain of these impacts in the coming days, and the economic repercussions. Since Jordanian economic growth was slow before the Covid-19 outbreaks, the economic contraction could be serious, and the government intervention would necessitate a cautious weighing of priorities and goals. Given that resources are limited, strategies that better handle the short-run crisis while yielding substantial long-run gains should be seriously considered. The economic effects of the COVID-19 have been highlighted in this study and emphasized policy options to reduce its effects. The study comes to the conclusion that monetary, macroprudential, and fiscal policy can help mitigate the effects of the COVID-19.

Keywords: Coronavirus Pandemic; COVID-19; Fiscal policy; Monetary Policy, Productivity Growth

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1. Introduction

Jordan bears a superfluous burden of poverty and unemployment, which be compounded by the COVID-19 epidemic. Although the situation is constantly changing, the original focus was on the clinical and epidemiological aspects of COVID-19, including measures to prevent transmission and infection. Fundamentally, the COVID-19 pandemic raised awareness that a sickness has no nationality and that we are all linked as one 'global nation.' The fact that coronaviruses do not respect national borders is at the heart of the global reaction and unity.

Jordan began taking precautionary measures early on. For example, thermal screening of passengers arriving. By early March, the government had drawn up plans to deal with a worsening of the pandemic in the country. In April, the Jordanian government stopped issuing new visas. Compulsory screening and quarantined for 14 days of all international

passengers arriving in Jordan. Moreover, all land borders with neighbouring countries were closed for passenger traffic. The virus, according to experts, will deliver a negative supply shock to the global economy by causing many industries to shut down and disrupting global supply lines (OECD, 2020). But how severe and long-lasting will this supply disruption be? Will this have an impact on aggregate demand? What is the best monetary policy response? What about fiscal policy? These are the topics of a contentious debate right now.

Given the huge uncertainty surrounding the future evolution of the epidemic, however, it is useful to work out the macroeconomic implications of more pessimistic scenarios. To do so, we highlight three results. First, the virus's spread might depress worldwide demand. Second, a supply-demand doom cycle might take place, exacerbating the virus-caused supply disruption. Third, the global economy may become subject to stagnation